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EDUCATIONAL MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT TO PROMOTE INTEGRATED MULTI-TROPHIC AQUACULTURE (IMTA) IN THE FRAME OF ASTRAL PROJECT

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Many of us are unaware of how our daily actions affect the health of the ocean, its sustainability and many of the resources we depend on. In addition, most of us do not know about the global reach and importance of the sea and oceans in medical, economic, social, political and environmental terms. To address these aspects, providing and improving access to accurate and reliable education about the marine environment is essential. Lately, many international communities have assigned a large portion of their budgets and efforts to research and innovation programs, in order to reinforce science activity on different topics. In this context, the All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) arises. ASTRAL is focused on Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) farming, aiming to define, support, and promote sustainable aquaculture production across the Atlantic area. IMTA is the farming of species from different trophic levels in a way that allows one species' uneaten feed and wastes to be used as inputs (fertilizers and feed) for another species. Sharing knowledge and capacity development are among ASTRAL priorities, as well as to build a collaborative ecosystem along the Atlantic Ocean with industrial partners, scientists, policymakers, social representatives, educators and other relevant stakeholders.

ASTRAL is committed to increasing the public acceptance and awareness of aquaculture by fostering public understanding of the value of aquaculture and especially IMTA, as a sustainable way to produce aquatic products. Teaching youngsters certain topics about sustainable aquaculture and more complex biological processes such as IMTA can be difficult, especially when resources are scarce and information is vast, and, in many cases, too technical or in English (most used language for scientific communications). Therefore, we have developed a compilation of activities (i.e. activity guide) that intends to disseminate scientific knowledge in a pedagogical and ludic way. This material aims to be a resource for teachers while teaching children between 10 to 15 years old, to convey basic knowledge about traditional aquaculture and IMTA. The guide addresses general concepts about aquaculture and fisheries, as well as more specific production methods such as IMTA and aquaponic systems. Thirty-seven (37) activities have been created including didactical tools such as: multiple choice, open questions, join with arrows schematics, find the differences schematics, crosswords, puzzles and others, to give the teachers more alternatives to engage with students. This guide has been translated into 3 languages (English, Spanish, Portuguese) being therefore available for more than 120 countries. We hope this educational guide results in an effective tool to foster dissemination strategies which are paramount within the realm of multitrophic aquaculture projects to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and public understanding.

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